

Phonological Domains in Meithei

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Primary Source(s)

Chelliah, Shobhana L. 1997. A grammar of Meithei. Mouton

I. Notes on syllable structure:

Default: C(C)V(C)

25 consonant phonemes, 6 vowel phonemes

Two-way tone contrast (high & low)

II. P-Rules & Processes, and the Morpho-Syntactic Information they

Reference

A. *V and *V.V (i.e. onset syllabification in different morpho-syntactic environments)

i. Word-initial, Prefix-Stem & Prefix-initial: ? insertion

- (1) /a-ibə/ (ATTRIB-write) > [ʔə-ʔibə] 'writer'
/yá-on/ (yield-turn) > [yá-ʔon] 'move'

ii. Stem-Suffix: Glide formation or Consonant gemination

- (2) ú-í (see-NON-HYP) > [úy]
təw-e (dig-ASSERT) > [təwwe] (p. 23)

B. Tone alternations

i. Special Tone alternation disyllabic suffixes: their own domain for tone spread

- (3) -ténə 'by V-ing'
-nébə 'in order to V'
-túnə 'Ving'
-lébə 'having V'ed' (p. 35)

ii. “Enclitic” (inflectional formative -í carries independent tone (p. 39)

iii. Domain for Tone upstep & downstep: stem ± either prefix and/or suffix
(exceptions in i & ii above)

refer to pitch trace charts on pages 27-34 in Chelliah 1997.

C. Assimilation

i. stop voicing assimilation: stem + suffix (not stem + prefix) & stem + stem (most but not all)

voiceless unaspirated stop onsets are voiced between voiced segments

(4) čá-pə (eat-NOM) > [čábə] (p. 49)
nú + túm > [núdúm] ‘stone’ (stone-pointed)

ii. l~nasal assimilation

anticipatory complete assimilation of lateral // to nasal
stem + suffix

(5) yəŋ-ləm-li (look-EVID-PROG) > [yəŋəmmi] ‘looking’ (p. 61)

D. Deaspiration

If an aspirated suffix or 2nd stem piece (in compounds) preceded by /h/ or an aspirated consonant, it deaspirates and then undergoes stop voicing assimilation

(6) thin-khət (pierce-UPWARD) > [thingət] ‘pierce upwards’

Can happen across compounds too, but process not as predictable (p. 55)

(7) phi + khét (conceal-place) > [phijét] ‘dress’

E. Deletion and Cluster Simplification via Deletion

i. k deletion

left edge of stem + suffix; followed by the l ~ r alternation

(8) thók-lək-pə (out-DIST-NOM) > [thórəkpə] ‘to come out’ (p. 60)

ii. k-l cluster reduction (l deletion)

spans a stem + suffix combination

(9) yok-lə-pə (rear-PERF-NOM) > [yokʔəbə] 'rear up' (p. 60)

followed by consonant gemination because of VV sequence, and then alternation to a kʔ sequence.

F. Phonotactic Constraints (consonants)

i. /r/ (alveolar trill) only in C2 onset position, word-medial čəm.pra 'lemon'

Otherwise, it is an allophone of /l/ in other environments

(10) čá-li > (eat-PROG) [čári] 'eating' (p. 21)

phu + lit (cloth + jacket) > [phurit] 'shirt'

mə-ləy-pák-tə (3P-land-broad-LOC) > [məɾəybáktə] (p. 402)

Not contrastive in word-initial position. Also, Cr clusters not in word-initial position

ii. In native words: *C if voiced stop (phoneme)

Meithei has phonemic voiced stops, but they do not occur left edge of stem (native words only). They are contrastive though in medial onset position:

(11) əpók-pə 'swollen-NOM' vs. əbok 'grandmother'

G. Phonotactic Constraints (vowels)

i. /a/ not in initial syllables

also not a prefix syllable, so does not occur at left edge of stem ± prefixes

ii. /ə/ schwa restricted

not the final syllable vowel in polysyllabic stem morphemes (± additional postposed formatives). But postposed formatives themselves can have schwa:

(12) -pə NOM; ténə BY

as can monomorphemic stems:

(13) čəy 'abuse' & prefixes mə 3P

III. Available Morpheme Types

stem, suffix, enclitic, prefix